

Synthesis and characterization of new crown ethers of Schiff base type and their complexes

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New crown ether ligands of Schiff base type (4-11) have been synthesised by the reaction of two equivalents of benzaldehyde, 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 2,3-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-methoxy-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with 2,3,5,6-di[4-aminobenzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (3). The ligand 2,3,5,6-di[4-*N*-(salicylidene)benzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (5) reacts with Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} to yield 1 : 1 metal-ligand complexes. The structures of ligands and complexes have been investigated by elemental analysis, IR, UV-visible, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR data. The tetradentate nature of the ligands is inferred from IR spectra. The UV-visible spectral data suggest octahedral geometry for metal complexes. The antimicrobial activities and yeast cultures of the ligands and metal complexes have been screened *in vitro* against the organisms *Escherichia coli* ATCC 11230, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 P, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 7064, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 8427, *Salmonella typhimurium* DSM 554, *Corynebacterium xerosis* ATCC 373 and *Hanseniaspora guilliermondii* DSM 3432, *Rhodotorula rubra* DSM 70403 and *Kluyveromyces fragilis* ATCC 8608. The metal complexes are more fungitoxic than the free ligand.

The study of macrocyclic ethers has attracted great interest in the last decades, not only from the synthetic and selective alkali and alkaline earth cation complexation properties point of view, but also with respect to their unusual characteristics^{1,2}. For the linkage of two crown ether units by means of aliphatic or aromatic chains, ester³⁻⁵, amide^{6,7} and Schiff base type⁸⁻¹⁰ precursors are commonly used. Macrocyclic polyethers form complexes with alkali metals, alkaline earth metals, and with some other metal ions, with oxonium ions, with protonated amines including amino acids, and also with some neutral and like molecules such as acetonitrile. In addition to the homonuclear mono- and ditopic complexes of bis(crown ethers) with alkali and alkaline earth metal ions, heteroatoms of the linkage unit between the two crown ether rings can form complexes with transition metal cations¹¹ to yield interesting heteronuclear oligotopic complexes of bis(crown ethers) in solution and in the solid state¹. Complexes of this type may be used as simple models for biological systems such as metalloenzymes¹².

In this paper, the new macrocyclicpolyether ligands of Schiff base type have been synthesized by the reaction of diamino crown ether (3) with benzaldehyde, substituted 2-hydroxy-1-benzaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. The metal complexes of 2,3,5,6-di[4-*N*-(salicylidene)

benzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (5) with Mn^{II} (5a), Fe^{II} (5b), Co^{II} (5c), Ni^{II} (5d), Cu^{II} (5e) and Zn^{II} (5f) have been synthesized (Scheme 1). The structures of the synthesized Schiff bases and their complexes were established by elemental analysis, IR, UV-visible, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra. The ligands and metal complexes have been screened techniques *in vitro* against the following microorganisms : *Escherichia coli* ATCC 11230, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 P, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 7064, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 8427, *Salmonella typhimurium* DSM 554, *Corynebacterium xerosis* ATCC 373, *Hanseniaspora guilliermondii* DSM 3432, *Rhodotorula rubra* DSM 70403 and *Kluyveromyces fragilis* ATCC 8608 by disc diffusion method^{13,14}.

Results and discussion

The elemental analyses suggest that all the complexes correspond to 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry (Table 2).

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra of compounds 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 show bands at 1624, 1621, 1619, 1617, 1618, 1622 and 1623 cm⁻¹ respectively for ν(C=N), 3436, 3474–3414, 3446, 3422, 3435 and 3415 cm⁻¹ for ν(O-H) indicating the Schiff bases formation (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11). The aryl and alkyl C-H stretching frequencies of compounds 4-11

Scheme 1

Table 1. Experimental and analytical data

Compd.	Formula	MA (g/mol)	Colour	Yield (%)	M.p (°C)	Calculated (%)			Found (%)		
						C	H	N	C	H	N
4	C ₃₃ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₄	520	White	66	109	76.15	6.15	4.56	75.34	6.46	5.43
5	C ₃₃ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₆	552	Yellow	80	175	71.73	5.79	5.07	70.13	5.65	5.10
6	C ₃₃ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₈	584	Yellow	57	168	67.8	6.16	4.79	68.01	6.13	4.71
7	C ₃₃ H ₃₆ N ₂ O ₈	612	Yellow	65	149	68.62	5.88	4.57	67.89	5.51	4.33
8	C ₃₃ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₆ Br ₂	710	Brownish yellow	47	245	55.77	4.22	3.94	54.87	4.77	3.80
9	C ₃₃ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₁₀	642	Yellow-red	37	202	61.68	4.67	8.72	60.98	4.57	8.68
10	C ₃₃ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₆	552	Yellow	76	162	71.73	5.79	5.07	71.13	5.63	5.03
11	C ₄₁ H ₃₆ N ₂ O ₆	652	Yellow	65	142	75.46	5.52	4.29	74.56	5.42	4.11

Table 2. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour	M.p (°C)	Metal%
			Found (Calcd.)
[MnL] (5a)	Brown	258 (Decomp.)	8.01 (8.57)
[FeL] (5b)	Dark-brown	268 (Decomp.)	8.50 (8.70)
[CoL] (5c)	Dark-brown	285 (Decomp.)	8.99 (9.13)
[NiL] (5d)	Dark-green	342 (Decomp.)	9.13 (9.10)
[CuL] (5e)	Black-green	276	9.25 (9.78)
[ZnL] (5f)	Yellow-green	257	9.95 (10.03)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses.

were observed at 3066, 3050, 3060, 3050, 3060, 3090, 3066 cm⁻¹ and 2918–2878, 2917–2879, 2933–2886, 2917–2878, 2923–2862, 2904–2862, 2925–2879 cm⁻¹ and ν(C–O–C) bands are observed at 1247–1144–1112–1064, 1272–1195–1151, 1280–1220–1036, 1258–1199–1127–1065, 1267–1179–1111, 1296–1253–1132 and 1258–1199–1127–1065 cm⁻¹, respectively. IR spectra of the complexes indicate that Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are coordinated to the inner N₂O₂ compartment. The ν(C=N) and ν(C–O) vibrations, which appear at 1621 and 1374 cm⁻¹, respectively, in the case of free ligands (5), are shifted to 1618–1361, 1617–1334, 1609–1342, 1619–1339, 1607–1338 and 1617–1341 cm⁻¹, respectively, in these complexes. The complexes, show bands at 378–384 cm⁻¹ due to ν(M–O). These indicate the presence of coordinated water.

Electronic spectra :

The UV-vis spectra of ligands 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 and complexes 5a, 5b, 5c, 5d, 5e and 5f were studied in DMSO. The compound 5, 6, 7, 8 and 10 do not show any absorption in the range >400 in DMSO. For compounds 9 and 11, a new band is observed at >400 nm in the same solvent¹⁷. Only phenolic imine tautomer is dominant in DMSO for 5, 6, 7, 8 and 10. On the other hand, the compounds 9 and 11 are in tautomeric equilibria (phenol-imine, O–H...N ⇌ keto-amine, O...H–N forms) in

DMSO^{18–20}. This tautomer is observed in DMSO for 9 and 11 as supported by UV-visible data, while for compound 9 and 11 it is not observed in DMSO by ¹H NMR. The keto-amine tautomer is observed 37% and 48% for compounds 9 and 11 in DMSO.

The Co^{II} complex shows absorptions at 31746 and 38461 cm⁻¹. The presence of two coordinated water molecules has already been confirmed by IR spectral data. The geometry may be octahedral. The Ni^{II} complex absorptions at 28011 and 38167 cm⁻¹. The nickel complex is octahedral similar to the cobalt complexes. The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} complex shows two bands at 28571 and 38461 cm⁻¹. The local symmetry around the manganese may be octahedral considering the two coordinated water molecules. The Cu^{II} complex shows absorptions at 33333 and 38167 cm⁻¹ indicating a octahedral geometry. The Zn^{II} complex has been assigned distorted octahedral geometry based on its absorptions. The former shows absorptions at 25000, 31545 and 38167 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR data of compounds 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 are given in Table 4. The ¹H NMR spectra of the compounds 5–11 show that the tautomeric equilibrium favours the phenol-imine in DMSO. The OH protons are observed as singlets at 13.57, 13.87, 13.68, 13.55, 16.36, 10.64 and 16.14 ppm for ligands 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 respectively. The azomethine protons are observed as singlets at 8.52, 8.92, 8.87, 8.96, 8.93, 10.37, 8.49 and 9.69 ppm for 4–11 respectively. The phenyl protons are observed as multiplet at δ 6.48–9.18 ppm for compounds 4–11. The proton of the etheric group at Ar–OCH₂ also gave a triplet at δ 4.18, 4.13, 4.13, 4.13, 4.25, 4.13, 4.09, 4.16 ppm and Ar–OCH₂OCH₂ gave a triplet at δ 3.91, 3.77, 3.77, 3.77, 3.78, 3.79, 3.76 and 3.92 ppm for 4–11 respectively. OCH₂ singlets appear at δ 3.80, 3.64, 3.64, 3.63, 3.59, 3.65, 3.63 and 3.65 ppm for compounds 4–11 respectively. The OCH₂ proton of the compound 7 gave a singlet at δ 3.81 ppm. The Ar–CH₂–Ar

protons appear as singlets between 3.32 and 3.78 ppm respectively

¹³C NMR spectra

The proton de-coupled ¹³C NMR spectra of 4-10 were analysed (Table 4), and it was concluded that the structures in solution are symmetrical

Screening for antimicrobial activities

Escherichia coli ATCC 11230, *Staphylococcus aureus*

ATCC 6538 P *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 7064 *Protococcus vulgaris* ATCC 8427 *Salmonella typhimurium* DSM 554, *Corynebacterium xerosis* ATCC 373 and *Hanseniaspora guilhermondii* DSM 3432 *Rhodotorula rubra* DSM 70403 and *Kluyveromyces fragilis* ATCC 8608 were used as bacteria and yeast cultures. The compounds were dissolved in DMSO to a final concentration of 30 µg/mL. Empty sterilized antibiotic discs having a diameter of 6 mm (Schleicher & Schull No 2668, Germany) were each impregnated with

Table 3 ¹H NMR spectral data (δ ppm) in DMSO

Compd	δ OH	δ N=CH	δ Ar H	δ ArOCH ₂	δ ArOCH ₂ CH ₂	δ OCH ₃	δ ArCH ₂ Ar	δ OCH ₃
4	-	8.52s 2H	6.96-7.91m 16H	4.18t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.69 Hz)	3.91t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.69 Hz)	3.80s 4H	3.78s 2H	
5	13.57s 2H	8.92s 2H	6.93-7.71m 14H	4.13t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.48 Hz)	3.77t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.48 Hz)	3.64s 4H	3.56s 2H	
6	13.87s 2H 9.35s 2H	8.87s 2H	6.75-7.40m 12H	4.13t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.57 Hz)	3.77t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.57 Hz)	3.64s 4H	3.32s 2H	
7	13.66s 2H	8.96s 2H	6.87-7.41m 12H	4.13t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.41 Hz)	3.77t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.41 Hz)	3.63s 4H	3.33s 2H	3.81s 6H
8	13.55s 2H	8.93s 2H	6.88-8.93m 12H	4.25t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.25 Hz)	3.78t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.25 Hz)	3.59s 4H	3.48s 2H	
9	16.36s 2H	10.37s 2H	6.91-9.18m 12H	4.13t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.56 Hz)	3.79t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.56 Hz)	3.65s 4H	3.64s 2H	
10	10.64 broad 2H	8.49s 2H	6.85-7.74m 14H	4.09t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.58 Hz)	3.76t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.58 Hz)	3.63s 4H	3.61s 2H	
11	16.14s 2H	9.69s 2H	6.48-8.55m 18H	4.16t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.74 Hz)	3.92t 4H (³ J _{HH} 4.74 Hz)	3.65s 4H	3.58s 2H	

s singlet t triplet m multiplet

Table 4 ¹³C NMR spectral data (δ ppm) in DMSO

Compd	R	R'	R''	R'''
4	H	H	H	H
5	OH	H	H	H
6	OH	OH	H	H
7	OH	H	H	OCH ₃
8	OH	H	H	Br
9	OH	H	H	NO ₂
10	H	H	OH	H

Compd	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15	C16	C17	C18
4	122.59	136.80	129.42	145.40	-	-	158.88	157.91	129.02	116.26	131.47	115.56	129.14	-	71.33	70.25	68.11	
5	116.06	161.04	120.47	159.50	123.48	134.11	163.64	161.99	119.89	117.35	133.19	117.39	131.67	61.06	70.82	69.81	68.28	
6	116.02	150.06	150.03	120.31	123.38	141.50	164.20	158.59	119.49	116.15	146.43	119.43	123.43	-	70.85	69.84	68.35	
7	114.09	158.62	120.20	124.61	162.27	123.46	165.15	151.24	119.34	115.76	148.70	116.08	141.41	-	70.82	69.81	68.28	56.70
8	111.43	161.62	123.60	158.54	121.43	141.19	164.70	160.99	119.78	115.90	136.36	116.09	126.72	61.03	73.19	70.83	69.77	
9	116.20	161.04	119.21	133.37	159.20	123.65	167.04	160.38	117.06	116.20	153.20	116.28	123.51	-	70.84	69.75	68.38	
10	115.70	145.61	122.95	158.82	-	-	161.15	157.49	116.44	115.79	131.20	116.19	128.59	-	70.82	69.87	68.17	

Table 5. Antimicrobial activity of the compounds

Microorganisms/Compd.	Diameter of inhibition zones (mm)															
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	5a	5b	5c	5d	5e	5f
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	10	10	11	12	9	14	11	12	12	10	14	14	14	17	18	13
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	11	12	10	10	10	13	12	10	10	12	13	15	13	14	18	14
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	10	12	12	11	11	11	12	12	12	13	14	16	15	13	17	15
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	12	11	12	12	14	9	13	13	12	13	14	15	13	14	20	15
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	12	13	9	12	11	12	12	11	11	12	13	18	16	16	15	15
<i>Corynebacterium xerosis</i>	13	12	13	10	10	12	15	13	10	14	19	18	21	20	24	19
<i>Kluyveromyces fragilis</i>	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10	9	15	12	12	–
<i>Rhodotorula rubra</i>	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10	10	13	10	15	–
<i>Hanseniaspora guilliermondii</i>	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	11	12	14	12	14	13

Inactive (–), moderately active (8–13); higher active (>14).
Includes diameter of disc (6 mm).

20 µL of solution. All the bacteria mentioned above were incubated at 30 ± 0.1°C for 24 h by inoculation into Nutrient Broth (Difco), and the yeasts studied were incubated in Malt Extract Broth (Difco) for 48 h. An inoculum containing 10⁶ bacterial cells or 10⁸ yeast cells/mL was spread on Mueller-Minton Agar (Oxoid) plates (1 mL inoculum/plate). The discs injected with solutions were placed on the inoculated agar by pressing slightly and incubated at 35°C (24 h) for bacteria, and at 25°C (72 h) for yeast. On each plate an appropriate reference antibiotic disc was applied depending on the test microorganisms^{13,14}. The data reported in Table 5 are the average data of three experiments.

Table 5 shows antimicrobial activities of compounds. Besides, the inhibition zones formed by standard antibiotic discs are indicated in Table 6. As can clearly be seen from Table 5, all compound show antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria but ligands have no antifungal activity against the yeast cultures in this study. Notably, the metal complexes are active against the yeasts. In classifying the antibacterial activity as Gram-positive or Gram-negative, it would generally be expected that a much greater number would be active against Gram-positive than Gram-negative bacteria¹⁵. However, in this study the compounds were active against both Gram (+) and Gram (–) bacteria. When the results obtained were compared to those of standard antibiotics, it was observed that compound 5e has the highest antimicrobial effect against both types of bacteria and the yeast cultures. *Staphylococcus aureus* is more susceptible to the compounds 5d and 5e, as compared to the standard antibiotics. Ligands show weak antimicrobial effect against *Corynebacterium xerosis*, metal com-

Table 6. Antimicrobial activities of some standard antibiotics

Microorganisms	Inhibition zone (mm)				
	P10	CTX30	VA30	SAM20	NY100
<i>S. aureus</i>	13	12	13	16	–
<i>E. coli</i>	18	10	22	12	–
<i>B. cereus</i>	14	14	18	16	–
<i>S. typhimurium</i>	13	13	18	12	–
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	10	18	20	14	–
<i>C. xerosis</i>	14	15	18	14	–
<i>K. fragilis</i>	–	–	–	–	18
<i>R. rubra</i>	–	–	–	–	18
<i>H. guilliermondii</i>	–	–	–	–	21

P10 : Penicillin G (10 units), CTX30 : Cefotaxime 30 µg, VA30 : Vancomycin 30 µg, SAM20 : Ampicillin 10 µg, NY100 : Nystatin 100 µg.

plexes have higher effect than all standard antibiotics. *Bacillus cereus* is more susceptible to the compounds 5b, 5c, 5e and 5f when compared to P10, CTX30 and SAM20. All metal complexes except 5a have higher effect than those of P10 and SAM20 against *Proteus vulgaris*. Similarly, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* are more susceptible. *Kluyveromyces fragilis* and *Rhodotorula rubra* as the yeast cultures are resistant to the compound 5f.

The compounds differ significantly in their activity against tested microorganisms. These differences may be attributed to the fact that the cell wall in Gram-positive bacteria of a single layer, whereas the Gram-negative cell wall is multi-layered structure and the yeast cell wall is quite complex¹⁶.

Conclusion :

The Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes have distorted octahedral structure with water-metal-water connection. The manganese, ferrum, cobalt, nickel and copper complexes are paramagnetic.

This study is a preliminary evaluation of antimicrobial activity of crown ether ligands of Schiff base type and metal complexes. It indicates that the compounds have the potential to generate novel metabolites. The compounds show broad spectrum activities. The metal complexes are more fungitoxic than the free ligand. The compounds could serve as selective agents for the maintenance of animal or human health from infections.

Experimental

Reagents and techniques :

The ¹H, ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DPX FT-NMR spectrometer operating at 400 and 101.6 MHz. The ¹H and ¹³C chemical shifts were measured using SiMe₄ as an internal standard. Infrared absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer BX II spectrometer in KBr discs. UV-vis were recorded on a Shimadzu 1201 series spectrometer. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were performed on a LECO CHNS-932 C-, H-, N- analyzer. Melting points were measured on a Electro Thermal IA 9100 apparatus using a capillary tube, THF, EtOH, DMSO, DMF, Na₂CO₃, (C₂H₅)₃N, triethyleneglycol, SOCl₂, hydrazine hydrate, benzaldehyde, 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 2,3-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-methoxy-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-nitro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and Pd-C (10%) were purchased from Merck (Germany).

Synthetic procedures :

Synthesis of 2,2'-methylenebis[4-nitrophenol] (1) and 2,3,5,6-di[4-nitrobenzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (2) :

2,2'-Methylenebis[4-nitrophenol] (1) and nitro crown ether (2) were prepared according^{17,18}.

Synthesis of 2,3,5,6-di[4-aminobenzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (3) :

To 2,3,5,6-di[4-nitrobenzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (2) (3.8 g, 0.0094 mol) and Pd/C (0.548 g, 10%) dissolved in ethanol (250 mL, 99%) was added dropwise hydrazine monohydrate (5.4 mL). The mixture stirred at reflux temperature for 3 h and then filtered through a pad of celite to remove the catalyst. Solvent and excess hydrazine were removed *in vacuo* to give the crude product

as a white solid which was used without further purification, m.p. 97°C, 2.93 g (90%) yield.

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

2,3,5,6-Di[4-N-(benzylidene)benzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (4) :

2,3,5,6-Di[4-aminobenzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (3) (0.20 g, 0.0058 mol) was added to a dry THF (100 mL) solution of benzaldehyde (1.23 g, 0.0116 mol). The mixture was stirred and heated for 3 h. Compound (4) was obtained from the evaporation of THF as a white solid, m.p. 109°C, 0.20 g (66 %) yield. Experimental and analytical data are summarized in Table 1.

Other Schiff base ligands were obtained using same method (Scheme 1). For all the compounds analytical and experimental details are given in Table 1.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

General method for preparation of [ML₁] complexes (M= Mn^{II} (5a), Fe^{II} (5b), Co^{II} (5c), Ni^{II} (5d), Cu^{II} (5e) and Zn^{II} (5f); H₂L₁, is the Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and 2,3,5,6-di[4-aminobenzo]-1,7,10,13-tetraoxacyclopentadeca-2,5-dien (5) :

A solution of metal(II) chloride (1 mmol) in methanol (50 mL) was mixed with a solution of the appropriate ligand (1 mmol) in methanol (50 mL) and heated for 75 min. The reaction mixture was cooled slowly and the solid product formed was filtered, washed several times with methanol and dried. For all complexes analytical and experimental details are given in Table 2.

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